

A Markovian Rock Mass Quality Q-based Prediction Model for Tunneling

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ABSTRACT: Prediction of rock mass condition is one of the most critical considerations in preliminary design stage of tunneling. Uncertainty in predicting the rock mass quality often leads to some conservatism, and significant deviations between predicted and actual results would cause project delay and cost overrun. Thus, to improve the prediction regarding uncertainties of rock mass condition, a rock mass classification Q prediction model based on the Markov process is presented. The model input, the transition intensity matrix and probabilistic description for Q-parameter states, can be derived from the available geological information. Based on the Markovian prediction approach, probabilistic distribution profiles for each state of Q-parameters can be obtained. The main output, the probabilistic distribution of Q-value, can be obtained accordingly by integrating distributions of all the Q-parameters along the alignment. The proposed prediction model has been validated by actual case study data from the Lion rock metro tunnel in Hong Kong. Sensitivity analysis has also been conducted and it shows J_a , J_n and J_r are the most sensitive input parameters. The probabilistic estimation of Q-value can be used to optimize the construction strategy in the planning and design stage, thus providing insightful information to practitioners in making decisions before tunnel construction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding of uncertainty in rock masses is one of the most important challenges during tunneling and underground construction. The ground conditions are never well known or understood before construction, and must be inferred or predicted based on available geological information (Guan et al., 2012). Mischaracterizing or disregarding the uncertainty of rock mass condition may cause project delay and cost overrun and even fatalities and casualties in some cases (Sousa and Einstein, 2012). On the other hand, if this uncertainty is well modeled before construction, it would be very helpful and can provide design aids for the subsequent underground construction (Spackova, 2012). In other words, the construction uncertainty would be reduced and the construction procedures can be optimized accordingly. Moreover, construction time and cost can also be optimized and could be helpful to the contract bidding and tendering (Min et al., 2008).

Several methods and techniques have been developed and used in geology prediction for the purpose of mitigating geological uncertainty in underground construction (Guan et al., 2012), including the neural networks (Lau et al., 2010), the geostatistical method (You and Lee, 2006; Ferrari et al., 2014; Chen et al., 2017), the displacement vector orientation analysis (Jeon et al., 2005) and Markov process approach (Chan, 1981; Ioannou, 1987; Guan et al., 2012). Among them, the Markov process approach is of interest since it considers each geological parameter as

a discrete-state continuous-space Markov process (Ioannou, 1987). The Markov process has been widely used in the tunneling field (Haas and Einstein, 2002; Ruwanpura et al., 2004; Min et al., 2008; Felletti and Beretta, 2009; Bi et al., 2015.). The Markov process is appropriate for geologic prediction in tunneling mainly due to the fact that this stochastic process involves not only uncertain geological parameters along the tunnel alignment but also their locations (Leu and Adi, 2011). Ashley et al. (1981) produced the competing hypotheses (best estimate, upper bound and lower bound) of transition probability and transition intensity coefficient for modelled geological parameters. Based on these hypotheses, geology predictions from each Markov model were weighted by the associated state probabilities of geologic parameters. Ioannou (1987) modelled geologic parameters as continuous-space, discrete-state Markov process along the tunnel alignment and proposed a general Markovian geologic prediction model for tunneling. In this model, a single probabilistic ground class profile was obtained by aggregating the probabilistic profiles of a set of geologic parameters (rock type, joint density, degree of weathering, water availability) along the tunnel alignment. Ruwanpura et al. (2004) used a simple two-state Markov Chain to determine the occurrence of soil type transition and to accurately predict the soil profiles between boreholes. Leu and Adi (2011) proposed a geological prediction model using Hybrid Neural-Hidden Markov Model, the combination of a Hidden Markov Model and a back propagation neural network. The probability profile of geology class,

described by soil parameters of SPT N value and clay content percentage, was obtained from an actual water tunnel in Taiwan and validated the proposed Neural-HMM model. Guan et al. (2012) combined the Markov random process and Bayesian updating procedure for dynamic prediction of geological conditions along the tunnel alignment. New geological mapping information at the tunnel face was used to update the prediction of geologic condition ahead of the advancing tunnel face. Based on the obtained probabilistic ground class profile along the tunnel, the construction cost was estimated probabilistically using work breakdown structure-based cost variance analysis (Guan et al., 2014).

In the field of tunneling, however, most of the geological conditions are described using a single set of conservative values for the worst scenario. This can be strongly biased and unreliable, which would lead to over-conservatism and thereby delay or cost overrun of the project (Langford, 2013). Generally, the vague descriptions and qualitative estimations are given for states of certain geological parameters, and these estimations are highly dependent on the on-site engineering geologists' experiences and knowledge. A good example is the vague evaluations about the weathering grade of rock masses like heavily weathered, moderately weathered, slightly weathered. In addition, the geological parameters in ground classification (GC), picked by the tunneling experts, may not be the most influential factors that well describe the rock mass condition and govern the ground behavior. Apart from that, it is found that for simplicity purpose, GC may have only a few geologic parameters and parameter states characterized by vague descriptions. For instance, the parameter of weathering degree has only two fuzzy states: severe and no severe (Ioannou, 1987). Moreover, most of current research and practice assume all the geological parameters to be independent, neglecting the inherent interdependency between certain parameters. It is also not uncommon that the corresponding single excavation-support method would be assigned to each GC category. This may highly depend on the expertise and may also be disputable among experts with different levels of knowledge and experiences. In other words, the uncertainty between the GC and excavation-support method is not considered. Last but not least, GC is mainly determined subjectively combing a few case-dependent geological parameters for local projects. Some issues may be encountered with regard to the international communication of practitioners in mega tunneling projects. Fortunately, almost all of the aforementioned weaknesses of GC can be dealt with the use of probabilistic rock mass classification.

A rock mass classification Q-system, proposed by Barton et al. (1974) for underground excavations and support requirements, has been widely used for classifying rock masses in tunneling. As a rock mass classification

method, Q system was established and developed based on thousands of case records from all over the world and contains six important general parameters that might be expected during underground opening excavation (Hoek, 2007). Compared with GC, it is helpful in international communication of practitioners in mega tunneling projects. In addition, in terms of its components, each Q-parameter (RQD, J_n , J_r , J_a , J_w , SRF) has several states with different quantitative ratings, providing relatively complete description of geological condition. In contrast, GC has only a few geological parameters and parameter states which are usually expressed by vague qualitative descriptions. Moreover, compared to GC, Q-value is the product of three quotients representing block size (RQD/J_n), joint friction characteristics (J_r/J_a) and active stress (J_w/SRF). Each Q-parameter has different impacts on the overall Q-value and the correlation between them can also be incorporated. This empirical Q-based rock classification system has defined several rock classes as well as several possible support patterns based on extensive global case records and updates (Hoek, 2007). It should also be noted that as an empirical rock mass classification system, Q system also has uncertainties in itself (Stille and Palmstrom, 2003; Palmstrom and Stille, 2010). The uncertainties involved in Q system should be considered and characterized in a probabilistic way.

The Markovian rock mass quality Q-based prediction model, the combination of the Markovian prediction approach and probabilistic rock mass classification Q system, is proposed in this paper. The probabilistic Q-value can be estimated along the tunnel alignment based on the available regional and local rock mass conditions using Markovian prediction technique. In this paper, the methodology of Markovian rock mass quality Q-based prediction is firstly introduced in Section 2. The Markovian prediction approach, which is based on Chan (1981) and Ioannou (1987), is reviewed in this section. A case study in a selected section of the Lion rock metro tunnel in Hong Kong has been used to validate the proposed prediction model. The main results and discussion on application of the proposed model are in Section 3. The main conclusions are summarized in Section 4.

2. METHODOLOGY OF THE PROPOSED PREDICTION MODEL

2.1. Markovian Prediction Approach

A stochastic process which has the Markov property is called a Markov process (Benjamin and Cornell, 2014). The Markov property, also named memoryless or single-step memory, means that the future behavior depends only on its present state and not on its past history (Benjamin and Cornell, 2014). The Markov process regards each geological parameter as independent continuous-space, discrete-state Markov process

(Ioannou, 1987). In other words, each geologic parameter is treated as a random process $X_{(t)}$ whose state probability is a function of time t . The term “time” can be equivalent to the location along the tunnel alignment where the location is identified by the distance u from a certain fixed point such as the tunnel portal (Chan 1981). Thus the Markov property describing the state probability for the process $X_{(t+1)}$ depends only on the previous most recent parameter state closest to the location $t_{(i+1)}$. The single step memory can be illustrated more clearly in form of mathematical terms as following:

$$P[X(t_{i+1})=x_{i+1} | X(t_i)=x_i, X(t_{i-1})=x_{i-1}, \dots] = P[X(t_{i+1})=x_{i+1} | X(t_i)=x_i] \quad (1)$$

where $t_{i+1}, t_i, t_{i-1}, \dots (t_{i+1} > t_i > t_{i-1} > \dots)$ are the locations along the tunnel alignment from an arbitrary origin (e.g. the tunnel portal), $x_{i+1}, x_i, x_{i-1}, \dots$ are the corresponding outcomes of the random variables $X(t_{i+1}), X(t_i), X(t_{i-1}), \dots$ at these locations respectively.

Three elements, including transition probability, transition intensity coefficient, and interval transition probability of geological parameter states, are the distribution parameters defining the Markov process in the field of geology prediction, and these can be estimated based on general geological information (Ioannou, 1987). The transition intensity matrix A , containing transition intensity coefficient c_i and transition probability P_{ij} , defines the Markov process completely.

$$A = [a_{ij}] \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (2)$$

$$\text{where } a_{ij} = \begin{cases} -c_i & i = j \\ c_i P_{ij} & i \neq j \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In the above, the parameter P_{ij} is defined as the probability of next geological parameter state is j given that the current state is i . It can be estimated as the ratio of number of transitions from state i to state j to the total number of transitions out of state i . The transition intensity coefficient c_i is related with the extent of a geological parameter state, which represents at what length the parameter state will persist before a transition to other state occurs. It has been proven that the extent follows exponential distribution and the transition intensity coefficient c_i of a parameter state is the reciprocal of its extent (Chan, 1981).

Both P_{ij} and c_i can be estimated by statistical procedures if there are sufficient relevant data from a region of similar geology as the tunnel project area. If the amount of data is insufficient in actual situations, subjective judgements from local experienced experts who are familiar with the geology of the tunnel region are needed. Note that constant P_{ij} and c_i values can only be applied independent of location within homogeneous Markov process regions with the same geologic history (Ioannou,

1987). In other words, if the tunnel project region is inhomogeneous and can be subdivided into several homogeneous areas, then both P_{ij} and c_i should be estimated separately for each area.

The interval transition probability matrix V , which is the matrix of interval transition probability v_{ij} , can describe the probabilistic behavior of a Markov process $X(t)$ over multiple transition intervals.

$$V(t_0, t) = [v_{ij}(t_0, t)] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } v_{ij}(t_0, t) = v_{ij}(t - t_0) = P[X(t) = j | X(t_0) = i] \quad (5)$$

where $V(t_0, t)$ is the interval transition probability matrix, $v_{ij}(t_0, t)$ is the interval transition probability, meaning the probability that Markov process $X_{(t)}$ will be in state j at location t given that it is in state i at location t_0 .

The interval transition probability $V_{(u)}$ of a Markov process satisfies the forward Kolmogorov differential equation, and it relates to the transition intensity matrix A .

$$\frac{dV(u)}{du} = V(u)A \quad (6)$$

The general solution of the above equation is as follows:

$$V(u) = e^{uA} = I + uA + (1/2!)u^2A^2 + \dots + (1/m!)u^m A^m + \dots \quad (7)$$

where I is the identity unit matrix, and $u=t-t_0$.

As mentioned above, the geological conditions between observation locations (e.g. boreholes) can be predicted by Markov process combing the general information-based interval transition probability matrix V_{ij} and the location-specific-based probabilistic geologic information. The state probability of a geologic parameter X between two boreholes can be determined as (Chan, 1981):

$$v_{Xmj}(t - t_{i-1}) = \sum_{m=1}^n P[X(t_{i-1}) = m] \sum_{k=1}^n P[X(t_i) = k] \frac{v_{Xjk}(t_i - t)v_{Xmj}(t - t_{i-1})}{v_{Xmk}(t_i - t_{i-1})} \quad (8)$$

where m and k are the states of geologic parameter X at observation location t_{i-1} and t_i ($t_i > t_{i-1}$), respectively. Location t is the arbitrary point between observation location t_{i-1} and t_i , and its state of parameter X is j .

Therefore, state probabilities of a geologic parameter at arbitrary location t can be calculated between two boreholes t_{i-1} and t_i . With the probabilistic observation results from the next adjacent borehole t_{i+1} , parameter state probabilities between boreholes t_i and t_{i+1} can be predicted similarly. Repeat this procedure for geologic prediction among boreholes, then the probabilistic state profile of each geologic parameter can be obtained along the tunnel alignment. For more details about the Markovian geologic prediction approach, please see reference (Chan, 1981).

2.2. Probabilistic Rock Mass Classification Q

Based on extensive case histories of underground constructions, Barton et al. (1974) from the Norwegian Geotechnical Institute proposed a rock mass classification system named rock mass quality Q for underground excavations and support requirements. The numerical value of Q varies on a logarithmic scale from 0.001 to a maximum of 1000 and is defined by (Hoek, 2007):

$$Q = \frac{RQD}{J_n} \times \frac{J_r}{J_a} \times \frac{J_w}{SRF} \quad (9)$$

where RQD is the Rock Quality Designation; J_n is the joint set number; J_r is the joint roughness number; J_a is the joint alteration number; J_w is the joint water reduction factor and SRF is the stress reduction factor.

Q has six important general parameters that might be expected during the underground excavation and each parameter has several states describing different geological scenarios (Hoek, 2007). There is a quantitative classification chart for rating of individual parameters to obtain the overall Q-value of a rock mass. Based on the determined numerical Q-value and equivalent dimension of the excavated opening, permanent rock support can be estimated according to the empirical rock support chart (Barton, 2002).

The Q-based rock classes (e.g. Q-value from 1 to 4 is categorized as poor rock) can be adopted instead of subjectively determined GC which are the combination of several project-specific geologic parameters (Shao et al., 2015). To be more specific, probabilistic distributions of Q-parameters can be derived from Q-log at each borehole. Combined with the Markovian prediction model in Section 2.1, probabilistic profile of each Q-parameter can be obtained along the tunnel alignment. Then according to the equation of overall Q-value in Section 2.2.1, the probabilistic distribution of Q-value can be obtained along the tunnel alignment using Monte Carlo Simulations. Based on the Q-based rock classification, the probabilistic distribution of Q-based rock class can be obtained.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Probabilistic Profile of Q-parameters

The states for each Q-parameter are defined and modified slightly based on state definitions and descriptions in Barton (2002). For example, RQD is defined to have 4 states: (1) State 1 with RQD between 0 and 25, indicating the very poor rock mass; (2) State 2 with RQD between 26 to 50, meaning the poor rock mass; (3) State 3 with RQD between 51 and 75, manifesting the fair rock mass; (4) State 4 with RQD between 76 and 100, representing the good rock mass. The state definitions, descriptions, ratings for each Q-parameter are in Appendix A in detail. It should be noted that for parameter SRF, the descriptions and ratings for squeezing and swelling rocks are not listed

here since these rock mass conditions are not dealt with in the following case study. In cases where squeezing and swelling rock mass conditions are expected, corresponding descriptions and ratings should be included in SRF.

The Lion rock tunnel, part of the ‘‘Shatin to Central Link project’’ for Hong Kong metro extension, is selected for validation of the proposed Q-based rock mass quality prediction model. The Lion rock tunnel is being constructed from Hin King Portal to Ma Chai Hang shaft using drill and blast. The tunnel is located predominantly within fresh to moderately decomposed granite and quartz monzonite and passes through some potential faults, shear and fracture zones. In this paper, a tunnel section with 864 m length containing 7 drilled boreholes is selected as the case study for validation. The tunnel advances in the direction from borehole 1 to 7, and the relative locations for these boreholes are shown in Table 1 assuming borehole BH 1 as the reference point. In the detailed site investigation stage, all these boreholes were Q-logged and the imperfect Q-log exploration results were obtained in form of probability distribution. For validation purpose, the information for borehole 1, 5 and 7 is assumed known while the information for borehole 2, 3, 4 and 6 is assumed unknown, which will be predicted by the proposed model and compared with the actual results.

Table 1. Relative locations of boreholes

Borehole No.	BH1	BH2	BH3	BH4	BH5	BH6	BH7
Distance (m)	0	20	165	330	591	764	864
Information Known/Unknown	Known	Assumed unknown	Assumed unknown	Assumed unknown	Known	Assumed unknown	Known

The rock mass conditions in the selected tunnel section are relatively homogeneous. This means that the transition probability and transition intensity coefficients of Q-parameters can be viewed as constant in the entire section. The transition probability and transition intensity coefficient are normally estimated by combining the statistical procedure and subjective assessment based on the general geologic information (e.g. geologic map, geologic profile). In this case study, due to the limited availability of the general rock mass condition, the transition intensity matrix is established based on the local information from three known boreholes. The transition intensity matrices of Q-parameters in this tunnel section are calculated and depicted in Appendix B. Table 2 shows the non-deterministic Q-log results in three known drilled boreholes.

Table 2. Occurrence probability of Q-parameter states at known boreholes

Parameter	States	Rating	Occurrence probability (%)
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			BH1	BH5	BH7
RQD	State 1	0-25	0	0	0
	State 2	26-50	0	4	0
	State 3	51-75	13	6	12
	State 4	76-100	87	90	88
J _n	State 1	0.5	0	46	0
	State 2	2	0	0	8
	State 3	3	0	10	0
	State 4	4	8	5	8
	State 5	6	50	19	12
	State 6	9	22	10	64
	State 7	12	20	0	0
	State 8	15	0	10	8
J _r	State 1	4	0	0	0
	State 2	3	38	75	44
	State 3	2	50	5	50
	State 4	1.5	12	5	0
	State 5	1	0	15	6
	State 6	0.5	0	0	0
	State 7	1	0	0	0
J _a	State 1	0.75	0	0	0
	State 2	1	15	56	22
	State 3	2	45	19	16
	State 4	3	8	5	28
	State 5	4	32	20	34
	State 6	6	0	0	0
	State 7	8	0	0	0
	State 8	12	0	0	0
	State 9	13	0	0	0
	State 10	20	0	0	0

Continued Table 2.

J _w	State 1	1	92	90	86
	State 2	0.66	8	10	14
	State 3	0.5	0	0	0
	State 4	0.33	0	0	0
	State 5	0.1	0	0	0
	State 6	0.05	0	0	0

SRF	State 1	10	0	0	0
	State 2	7.5	0	0	0
	State 3	5	0	0	0
	State 4	2.5	0	0	0
	State 5	1	100	100	100
	State 6	2	0	0	0
	State 7	50	0	0	0
	State 8	200	0	0	0
	State 9	400	0	0	0

The Markov process model is capable of incorporating the knowledge on both the general and particular geology in tunneling area (Chan, 1981). Based on the transition intensity matrixes of Q-parameters and the probabilistic exploration results of Q-parameter states at local boreholes, the probabilistic profile for each Q-parameter can be predicted along the tunnel axis using Markov prediction technique. This calculation process can be coded and performed by MATLAB (Mathworks, 2013) according to Eq. (8). The obtained occurrence probabilistic profiles of Q-parameters are shown in Fig. 1, respectively. It is found that the state occurrence probability of Q-parameter J_n, J_r and J_a change significantly along the axis in the tunnel section while there is only slight variation in terms of Q-parameter RQD, J_w and SRF. This agrees well with the general rock mass condition, that is, the highly jointed and heavily weathered rock masses in this section.

(a) RQD profile

(b) J_n profile

(c) J_r profile

(d) J_a profile

(d) J_w profile

(d) SRF profile

Fig. 1. Occurrence probability profile of Q-parameter states.

As mentioned above, since the rock tunnel is being constructed, the predicted occurrence probability of Q-parameter states can be compared to the actual ones at boreholes for validation purpose. Table 3 shows the comparative results of predicted and actual Q-parameter probability in BH 4. It can be seen that the predicted and actual probabilities are closer for some parameters (e.g. RQD, J_a, J_w, SRF) than others (e.g. J_n, J_r). However, the variations for some parameters are not as big. In general, there are no significant differences between the prediction and actual results, indicating the comparability. Recall that the model input, the transition intensity matrix, is obtained based on Q-log data in three known boreholes due to the limited access to general geologic information. It is pointed out the Q-log results from drilled cores do not capture well the characteristics of J_n and J_r (NGI, 2015), and this may result in the differences between predicted and actual results at boreholes. If the general geological information is available and used to establish the transition intensity matrix as the model input, the good

agreement between prediction and actual results would be expected.

Table 3. Comparison of predicted and actual probability of Q-parameter states at BH 4

States	State probability of Q-parameters (%)											
	RQD		J _n		J _r		J _a		J _w		SRF	
	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted
State 1	0	0	0	25	0	0	0	0	77	92	0	0
State 2	8	0	0	0	54	66	30	32	23	8	0	0
State 3	16	8	0	0	22	32	30	29	0	0	0	0
State 4	76	92	16	1	16	1	9	9	0	0	8	0
State 5			21	38	8	1	22	31	0	0	92	100
State 6			39	33	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
State 7			8	1	0	0	9	0			0	0
State 8			8	1			0	0			0	0
State 9			8	0			0	0			0	0
State 10							0	0				

3.2. Probabilistic Profile of Q-value and Q-based Tunnel Support Pressure

As the distributions of Q-parameters are obtained along this tunnel section, the resultant probability distribution function (PDF) of overall Q-value can be calculated by Monte Carlo simulation (MCS) according to Eq. (9). In this example, @risk software (Palisade, 2012) was used with 5000 iterations to perform the MCS and the distributions of resultant Q-value were obtained. Fig. 2 illustrates an example of the obtained PDF and cumulative density function (CDF) of Q-value at a certain location. The distribution fit result by @risk software shows the log-normality of Q-value, which can also be seen in Fig. 2(a). The obtained full probability distribution of Q-value can be used for the subsequent probabilistic tunnel design purposes. Analogously, the distributions of Q-value can be derived at other locations, and thereby the Q-value distribution would be obtained along the entire tunnel alignment.

(a) Probabilistic distribution function (PDF) of Q-value

(b) Cumulative distribution function (CDF) of Q-value

Fig. 2. Distribution of Q-value at a certain location.

Barton et al. (1974) obtained the empirical relationship between required tunnel support pressure p_i (in unit of MPa) and Q-value. When the joint set number is less than three ($J_n < 9$), the support pressure is given as:

$$p_i = \frac{0.2\sqrt{J_n}}{3J_r} Q^{-\frac{1}{3}} \quad (10)$$

When the joint set number is not less than three (J_n is not less than 9), the pressure is expressed as:

$$p_i = \frac{0.2}{J_r} Q^{-\frac{1}{3}} \quad (11)$$

Take the average of Eq. (10) and (11), the PDF and CDF of average support pressure can be obtained given the statistical distribution of Q-value. Fig. 3 shows the distribution of support tunnel pressure provided the PDF and CDF of Q-value in Fig. 2 at the same location. The distribution fit results also show that the support pressure is log-normally distributed with positive skewness. Similarly, the statistical distribution of required support pressure can be obtained along the tunnel axis, assisting in the decision making for tunnel support design.

(a) PDF of support pressure

(b) CDF of support pressure

Fig. 3. Distribution of support pressure at a certain location.

3.3. Probabilistic Profile of Q-based Rock Class

Given the statistical distribution of Q-value, as shown in Fig. 2, the relative percentage of Q-based rock classes (RC) can be derived. Modified from Barton (2002), RC1–4 herein represent the very good rock, good rock, fair rock and poor rock with Q value within $Q > 40$, 10–40, 4–10, 1–4, respectively. The occurrence probability of Q-based rock classes has been obtained along the selected tunnel section, as illustrated in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the most dominant rock class is RC2 with good rock in the majority of this section, except for RC1 with very good rock within a 25 m zone (Distance 435–675 m) and RC3 with fair rock within a 60 m zone (Distance 804–864 m). Obviously, this can provide the relative percentage of rock mass classes along the tunnel section. The transition of dominant rock classes should be treated with care since it may indicate the significant variation of rock mass condition (e.g. between the good rock and poor rock) and the resultant transition of construction strategies.

The comparison of predicted and actual rock mass class can be used to investigate the accuracy of prediction model (Panthi and Nilsen, 2007). Table 4 compares the predicted and actual statistical distributions of Q-based rock classes in assumed unknown boreholes. Note that rock mass condition in BH2, 3, 4 and 6 is assumed

unknown and the predicted results in these boreholes can be compared with the actual ones. It is seen in Table 4 that the predicted and actual results are comparable despite some marginal deviations. Take BH2 as an example, both predicted and actual results show that RC2 is most likely followed by RC3 and RC4. The good agreement between predicted and actual Q-log results validates well the application of the proposed prediction model.

Fig. 4. Occurrence probability profile of Q-based rock classes.

Given the statistical distribution of Q-based rock class, the distribution of support class can also be obtained based on the Q-based support chart (NGI, 2015). Combined with the probability distribution of support pressure demonstrated in Fig. 3, the distribution of support class can provide decision aids for the selection of appropriate support scheme.

Table 4. Comparison of Q-based rock class distribution for predicted and actual results at boreholes

RC	Occurrence probability of Q-based rock class (%)							
	BH 2		BH 3		BH 4		BH 6	
	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted	Actual	Predicted
RC1	0	7	8	20	12	41	5	26
RC2	55	51	52	49	55	34	50	40
RC3	33	37	25	29	25	23	30	30
RC4	12	5	15	2	8	2	15	4

3.4. Sensitivity Analysis

There are several ranking techniques for relative importance of input parameters, including the differential sensitivity analysis, one at a time sensitivity analysis, factorial design, the sensitivity index and the importance factors (Hamby, 1994). The sensitivity analysis of Q-value to its input Q-parameters was carried out using @risk software. Fig. 5 demonstrates the rankings of relative importance for Q-parameters by the effect on output mean, the regression coefficient, the Spearman correlation coefficient and the contribution to output variance, respectively. Results show that the ranking of relative importance for Q-parameters is the same in terms

of these four different ranking techniques, that is, in the decreasing order: J_a , J_n , J_r , RQD, SRF and J_w . The great sensitivities of parameters J_a , J_n and J_r agree well with the general geologic condition, which is the variable weathered (fresh to moderately decomposed) granite ground with a few major and minor joint sets plus random joints. The obtained sensitivity results are also in accord with the different variation trends for occurrence probabilities of Q-parameters shown in Fig. 1. The significant changes in occurrence probabilities of parameter J_a , J_n and J_r manifest the higher sensitivity while the marginal variations for parameter RQD, J_w and SRF may illustrate the lower importance.

(a) Ranked by effect on output mean

(b) Ranked by regression coefficient

(c) Ranked by Spearman correlation coefficient

(d) Ranked by contribution to variance

Fig. 5. Rank of relative importance for Q-parameters.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It is of great significance and benefits to account for and model the uncertainties involved in rock mass characterization and classification in tunneling or underground construction field. The proposed Markovian rock mass quality Q-based prediction model, which is the combination of Markovian prediction approach and the probabilistic evaluation of rock mass quality Q, is capable of predicting rock mass quality before construction and characterizing the uncertainty involved. Based on the transition intensity matrixes (transition probability and transition intensity coefficients) of Q-parameter states, which can be estimated from available geological information, the probabilistic distribution profiles for each state of Q-parameters can be derived along the tunnel axis. The probability distribution of overall Q-value can be thereby obtained by combining the distributions of each Q-parameter using Monte Carlo simulations by @risk software. Given the probabilistic distribution of Q-value, the full probability distribution of tunnel support pressure can be obtained based on the empirical relationship between support pressure and Q-value. Moreover, the probabilistic profile of rock classes can also be derived along the tunnel alignment according to the Q-based rock mass classification provided the probabilistic distribution of Q-value.

A case study of a metro tunnel project with Q data collected from core logging has been used to validate the proposed Q-based prediction model. The selected rock tunnel section is being constructed, so the predicted results have been compared to the actual ones at boreholes for validation purpose. The comparability between predicted and actual results (the statistical distribution of Q-parameter states and Q-based rock classes) at boreholes have proved the validity of the proposed prediction model. In addition, sensitivity analysis has been performed in this case study and J_a , J_n and J_r are found to be the most sensitive input parameters. Overall, the proposed Markovian rock mass quality Q-based prediction model provides the probabilistic prediction of

rock mass quality in unexcavated tunnel section before construction accounting for uncertainties involved in rock mass classification. The predicted probabilistic distributions of Q-value can be used to prepare and optimize the construction strategy (tunnel excavation and support scheme) and to evaluate the uncertain construction time and cost, thus providing decision support for design in tunneling or underground construction.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A Definitions and ratings for Q-parameters (modified from Barton, 2002)

Table A1. States, descriptions and ratings for RQD

States	Descriptions	Rating
1	Very poor	0-25
2	Poor	26-50
3	Fair	51-75
4	Good	76-100

Table A2. States, descriptions and ratings for J_n

States	Descriptions	Rating
1	None	0.5
2	One	2
3	One plus	3
4	Two	4
5	Two plus	6
6	Three	9
7	Three plus	12
8	Four or more	15
9	Earth	20

Table A3. States, descriptions and ratings for J_r

States	Descriptions	Rating	
1	Discontinuous	4	
2	Undulating	Rough undulating	3
3		Smooth undulating	2
4	Slickensided undulating or Rough planar		1.5
5	Planar	Smooth planar	1
6		Slickensided planar	0.5
7	No contact when sheared		1

Table A4. States, descriptions and ratings for J_a

States	Descriptions	Rating	
1	Healed	0.75	
2	Unaltered joint wall	1	
3	No fills	Slightly altered wall	2
4		Coated non-softening	3
5		Coated softening or disintegrated sandy particles	4
6	Thin fills	Thin non-softening clay fillings	6
7		Thin softening clay fillings	8
8		Thin swelling clays	12
9	Thick fills	Thick, continuous; clay band; medium to low over-consolidated	13
10		Thick, continuous; clay band; swelling clay	20

Table A5. States, descriptions and ratings for J_w

States	Descriptions	Approx. water press. (kg/cm ²)	Rating
1	Dry	<1	1
2	Wet	1-2.5	0.66
3	High pressure in unfilled joints	2.5-10	0.5
4	High pressure with fillings outwash	2.5-10	0.33
5	Exc. inflows with decay	>10	0.1
6	Exc. inflows without decay	>10	0.05

Table A6. States, descriptions and ratings for SRF

States	Descriptions	Sigma c/ Sigma l	Rating
1	Multiple clay zones		10
2	Multiple non-clay zones		7.5
3	Single weak zone (Depth<50m) or heavily jointed		5
4	Single weak zone (Depth>50m) or low stress(>200)		2.5
5	Medium stress	200-10	1
6	High stress with tight structure	10-5	2
7	Moderate slabbing	5-3	50
8	Slabbing and rock burst	3-2	200
9	Heavy rock burst	<2	400

APPENDIX B Transition intensity matrices for Q parameters

Table B1. Transition intensity matrix of RQD

A _{ij} (‰)	1	2	3	4
1	-250	10	24	216
2	0	-28	3	25
3	0	1	-12	12
4	0	0	1	-1

Table B2. Transition intensity matrix of J_n

A _{ij} (‰)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	-13	0	0	1	4	4	2	1	0
2	23	-250	5	22	71	73	44	9	4
3	5	0	-58	5	17	17	10	2	1
4	1	0	0	-13	4	4	3	1	0
5	1	0	0	1	-4	2	1	0	0
6	1	0	0	0	2	-4	1	0	0
7	1	0	0	1	2	2	-7	0	0
8	3	0	1	3	9	10	6	-32	1
9	7	0	1	6	21	21	13	3	-73

Table B3. Transition intensity matrix of J_r

A _{ij} (‰)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	-500	223	202	43	32	0	0
2	0	-3	2	0	0	0	0
3	0	2	-3	0	0	0	0
4	0	7	6	-14	1	0	0
5	0	9	8	2	-18	0	0
6	0	446	404	86	64	-1000	0
7	0	446	404	86	64	0	-1000

Table B4. Transition intensity matrix of J_a

A _{ij} (‰)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	-1000	208	286	113	374	0	19	0	0	0
2	0	-6	2	1	3	0	0	0	0	0
3	0	1	-4	1	2	0	0	0	0	0
4	0	2	3	-10	4	0	0	0	0	0
5	0	1	1	1	-3	0	0	0	0	0
6	0	208	286	113	374	-1000	19	0	0	0
7	0	13	18	7	24	0	-63	0	0	0
8	0	208	286	113	374	0	19	-1000	0	0
9	0	208	286	113	374	0	19	0	-1000	0
10	0	208	286	113	374	0	19	0	0	-1000

Table B5. Transition intensity matrix of J_w

A _{ij} (‰)	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	-1	1	0	0	0	0
2	14	-14	0	0	0	0
3	918	82	-1000	0	0	0
4	918	82	0	-1000	0	0
5	918	82	0	0	-1000	0
6	918	82	0	0	0	-1000

Table B6. Transition intensity matrix of SRF

A _{ij} (‰)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	-1000	0	0	15	985	0	0	0	0
2	0	-1000	0	15	985	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	-1000	15	985	0	0	0	0
4	0	0	0	-76	76	0	0	0	0
5	0	0	0	1	-1	0	0	0	0
6	0	0	0	15	985	-1000	0	0	0
7	0	0	0	15	985	0	-1000	0	0
8	0	0	0	15	985	0	0	-1000	0
9	0	0	0	15	985	0	0	0	-1000

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